

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office
U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service
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In Reply Refer to:
2022-0048737-S7-001

October 14, 2022

Sarah Firestone
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San Francisco District
450 Golden Gate Avenue
San Francisco, CA 94102

Subject: Formal Consultation for the Reauthorization of the Department of the Army Regional General Permit No. 4 for the Continued Maintenance of Existing Water Circulation Ditches for the Purpose of Mosquito Abatement in Tidal Marshes for Alameda, Napa, Marin, San Mateo, and Sonoma Counties, California (Corps File No. SPN-2007-400304S)

Dear Ms. Firestone:

This letter is in response to the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers' (Corps) May 27, 2022, request to initiate formal consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) on the Continued Maintenance of Existing Water Circulation Ditches for the Purpose of Mosquito Abatement in Tidal Marshes for Alameda, Napa, Marin, San Mateo, and Sonoma Counties, California Project (project). The Corps received a request from the California Department of Public Health, on behalf of the County Mosquito and Vector Control Agencies for Alameda, Napa, Marin, San Mateo and Sonoma Counties (applicants), to reauthorize the regional general permit for mosquito abatement activities within their respective Mosquito Abatement Districts (District). The Corps determined that the project may affect, and is not likely to adversely affect the endangered California seablite (*Suaeda californica*), the endangered soft bird's-beak (*Cordylanthus mollis* ssp. *mollis*) and its designated critical habitat, the threatened delta smelt (*Hypomesus transpacificus*), the endangered California least tern (*Sternula antillarum browni*) (CLT), and the western snowy plover (*Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus*) (WSP). The Corps has also determined that the proposed project may affect, and is likely to adversely affect, the endangered California clapper rail (*Rallus obsoletus obsoletus*) (CCR), and the endangered salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*) (SMHM). The Corps' letter was received by the San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office (BDFWO) on May 27, 2022. This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*) (Act), and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to interagency cooperation (50 CFR 402).

Recent genetic analyses of rail species resulted in a change in the common name and taxonomy of the large, “clapper-type” rails (*Rallus longirostris*) of the west coast of North America to Ridgway’s rail (*Rallus obsoletus*) (Maley and Brumfield 2013; Chesser *et al.* 2014). Thus, the California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) is now referred to in the scientific community as the California Ridgway’s rail (*Rallus obsoletus obsoletus*). Until the Service officially publishes the adoption of recent nomenclature changes made by the American Ornithologists’ Union to Ridgway’s Rail (*Rallus obsoletus*) in the Federal Register, we maintain the use of California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) in this correspondence.

On July 5, 2022, the U.S. District Court of the Northern District Court of California vacated the 2019 regulations implementing section 7 of the Act. On September 21, 2022, the Ninth Circuit Court of Appeals granted a request to stay the U.S. District Court of Northern California’s July 5, 2022, order that vacated the 2019 Act regulations. As a result, the 2019 regulations are again in effect, and the Service has relied upon the 2019 regulations in rendering this biological opinion. However, because the outcome of the legal challenges to 2019 Act Regulations is still unknown, we considered whether our substantive analyses and conclusions in this consultation would have been different if the pre-2019 regulations were applied. Our analysis included the prior definition of “effects of the action,” among other prior terms and provisions. We considered all the “direct and indirect effects” and the “interrelated and interdependent activities” when determining the “effects of the action.” As a result, we determined the substantive analysis and conclusions would have been the same, irrespective of which regulations applied.

On July 5, 2022, the U.S. District Court of the Northern District Court of California vacated the 2019 regulations implementing section 7 of the Act. On September 21, 2022, the Ninth Circuit Court of Appeals granted a request to stay the U.S. District Court of Northern California’s July 5, 2022, order that vacated the 2019 Act regulations. As a result, the 2019 regulations are again in effect, and the Service has relied upon the 2019 regulations in issuing our written concurrence on the action agency’s “may affect, not-likely-to-adversely-affect” determination. However, because the outcome of the legal challenges to the 2019 Act regulations is still unknown, we considered whether our substantive analyses and conclusions would have been different if the pre-2019 regulations were applied in this informal consultation. Our analysis included the prior definition of “effects of the action.” We considered all the “direct and indirect effects” and the “interrelated and interdependent activities” when determining the “effects of the action.” We then considered whether any “effects of the action” that overlap with applicable ranges of listed species and critical habitat designations would be wholly beneficial, insignificant, or discountable to the species and critical habitat designations. As a result, we determined the substantive analysis and conclusions would have been the same, irrespective of which regulations applied.

In considering your request, we based our evaluation on the following: (1) the Corps’ May 27, 2022, request for initiation of formal consultation letter; (2) the October 2021, *Mosquito Source Reduction Activities in Tidal and Historically Marshlands of Some San Francisco Bay Area Counties - Biological Assessment* (BA) prepared by ESA; (3) the previous biological opinion for the project (Service File No. 08FBDT00-2015-F-0032); and (4) other information available to the Service.

The Service concurs with the determination that the project as proposed is not likely to adversely affect the California seablite. The only known population in the Action Area is located at the Emeryville Crescent State Marine Reserve (Reserve) in Alameda County and the Corps' applicant is proposing to coordinate with the Reserve to fully avoid the areas where the plant is located during project actions.

The Service concurs with the determination that the project as proposed is not likely to adversely affect the soft bird's-beak or its designated critical habitat. Approximately 379 acres of the Action Area are within critical habitat Unit 1. The applicants are proposing to avoid the soft bird's-beak to the fullest extent possible. Prior to any mosquito source reduction activity, the applicants are proposing to make a diligent effort to identify known locations of soft bird's-beak. This will include requests for information from appropriate Federal and state sources for known populations. Work sites near active populations and within suitable habitat for this species will be surveyed by a Service-approved biologist with demonstrable appropriate botanical expertise to exclude locations with soft bird's-beak populations from active project activities. While work authorized under the proposed regional general permit would be conducted between the period of August 1 through January 31, to the extent possible, work will be conducted in the blooming season (June/July to September/October) when the plant is readily identifiable. Locations of soft bird's-beak will be flagged, and a buffer area of at least 30 feet will be established to exclude activities that would directly remove or alter the habitat of this plant species. Flags might be removed upon completion of work activities but will generally be retained to minimize risks of disturbance. Carefully walking near the plants to verify their distribution and establish exclusion markers is not considered an activity that would remove or alter the habitat of these plants. Project activities are not expected to alter or diminish the critical habitat. Impacts will be limited to vegetation removal within drainage ditches and minor ditch excavations. These are expected to be temporary and not affect the primary constituent elements in Unit 1. Additionally, there is potential for improvements to tidal marsh habitat from the clearing of ditches which will improve aquatic flow.

Upon reviewing the project and potential effects to delta smelt, the Service concurs with the determination that the project as proposed is not likely to adversely affect the delta smelt. This determination is based on the description of the habitats being affected and the unlikelihood of delta smelt being in the Action Area at the time of the proposed work. In the Napa County District, the project is described as only taking action within the circulation ditches when they have lost tidal connectivity to the open water environments where delta smelt occupy or have had that connectivity impaired such that water quality conditions are no longer conducive to supporting delta smelt. Delta smelt are not expected to occur in the San Pablo or San Francisco Bays during project implementation. The project does not occur within delta smelt designated critical habitat.

The Service concurs that the project as proposed is not likely to adversely affect the CLT or the WSP. This is based on the applicants' proposal to coordinate with the Napa-Sonoma Wildlife Area, the Don Edwards San Francisco Bay National Wildlife Refuge, the San Pablo Bay National Wildlife Refuge, and the Alameda Wildlife Reserve regarding the locations and avoidance of any CLT or WSP nests near tidal marsh work areas. CLT are colonial ground-nesting seabirds. Their preferred nesting habitat consists of undisturbed stretches of sparsely vegetated sandy or gravel substrate, adjacent or close to aquatic foraging areas. These areas include sandy beaches and salt flats. Nesting habitat for WSP includes sandy coastal beaches

with little to no vegetation above the high tide line, dry salt ponds, and river bars. CLT and WSP are known to nest in District counties, but are not expected to nest within tidal marsh habitat where work is proposed. CLT and WSP may roost on roads or levees that provide access to project sites. The Districts are proposing to avoid any potential nesting areas and limit vehicle traffic to a 10 mile per hour speed limit in areas that may potentially be used by CLT or WSP. The project does not occur within WSP designated critical habitat.

The remainder of this document represents the Service's biological opinion on the effects of the project to CCR and SMHM.

CONSULTATION HISTORY

May 27, 2022	The Service received the consultation request from the Corps.
June 1, 2022	The Service sent an email to the Corps requesting whether the Corps wanted to proceed with an amendment to, an extension for, or reinstate the prior consultation for the project. The Corps responded that as they were deciding which option to pursue, the Corps mistakenly included Suisun thistle in the consultation request. The Corps requested to remove the Suisun thistle from the consultation as it did not occur in the Action Area with the removal of the Solano County District as an applicant from the consultation. The Corps and the Service held a telephone conversation upon receiving the Corps email response and determined that a new consultation would be appropriate.

BIOLOGICAL OPINION

Description of the Proposed Action

The Corps is proposing to issue a 5-year regional general permit to the County Mosquito and Vector Control Agencies for Alameda, Napa, Marin, San Mateo and Sonoma Counties. The applicants are seeking reauthorization of ongoing activities for the maintenance of existing, currently serviceable water circulation ditches for the purpose of mosquito abatement in tidal marshes. Maintenance does not include any modification that changes the character, scope, or size of the original ditch designs.

Within tidal marsh habitats, mosquito source reduction is generally accomplished through excavation and maintenance of circulation ditches to facilitate efficient tidal exchange. Other mosquito source reductions may include the management and maintenance of water control structures (e.g. tide gates and culverts) and vegetation removal/trimming. This may also include the fill of non-functioning ditches and site access associated with the aforementioned actions. Circulation ditches are designed to reduce stagnant water conditions and to enhance access for fish that prey on mosquitos through tidal circulation. Circulation ditches are generally small in size with "V" shaped configurations, but can be medium to large ditches in order to increase drainage or flow. Typical maximum dimensions for small circulation ditches are 12-inch bed

width, 24-inch top of bank opening width, and 18 inches maximum depth at thalweg. Maximum dimensions for medium to large circulation ditches are 5 feet top of bank opening and 4 feet maximum depth with variable side slopes.

The Districts primarily utilize manual labor and hand tools to conduct the source reduction actions; however, the Marin/Sonoma Districts periodically enlist the use of larger equipment such as rotary ditchers and low ground pressure excavators for ditch excavation and maintenance actions. This equipment is generally used to maintain the larger sized ditches, ditches of substantial length or when conditions preclude the use of hand tools. Equipment that utilizes a rotary ditcher attachment side casts ditch spoils in a slurry which is sprayed up to approximately 50 feet from the circulation ditch. This minimizes the volume of spoils placed immediately alongside the ditches and eliminating the need to further spread the spoils. It also serves to reduce the potential for creating conditions favorable to colonization by invasive plant species (e.g. *Lepidium latifolium*). Filling of non-functioning ditches involve plugging the ditch with marsh soils through the use of hand tools and or low ground pressure excavators for medium to large ditches.

Water control structures repair or replacement actions are not frequently undertaken by the Districts. Repairs are performed as necessary to restore the affected structure to its original or minimum desired function. Such actions could involve limited vegetation removal and/or clearing/excavating associated circulation ditches.

All of the described actions require access by the District personnel into the tidal marsh habitats. This may require the use of all-terrain vehicles or an Argo (one or two person vehicles with tracks).

Work authorized under the proposed regional general permit would be conducted between the period of August 1 through January 31.

Conservation Measures

1. General

- Workers participating in mosquito source reduction actions shall receive environmental awareness training given by a Service-approved biologist prior to commencing work in tidal marsh habitats. At a minimum, this training will include an overview of the laws that protect the federally listed species with potential to occur in the work areas. This will also include the guidelines outlined in *Walking in the Marsh: Methods to Increase Safety and Reduce Impacts to Wildlife/Plants* (Service 2013).

2. CCR and SMHM

- A Service-approved biologist will be present during work within potential CCR and SMHM habitat.

- Activities within CCR and SMHM habitat will be avoided within two hours before or after extreme high tides (mean higher high water) or when the marsh plain is inundated. Exceptions may be made for addressing issues that require immediate attention.
- Vegetation removal within CCR or SMHM habitat will be limited to the minimum amount necessary to allow the required project action to be accomplished.
- Prior to commencement of work in areas containing suitable SMHM habitat where work will involve use of large equipment, such as the rotary ditcher, efforts will be made to ensure the SMHM are not present by first removing suitable marsh vegetation within the immediate area. To the extent practicable this will be accomplished using hand tools. This will likely discourage SMHM from entering the area and reduce the risk of injury or mortality.
- To the extent feasible, work involving the removal of high marsh vegetation (potential nesting habitat), ditch excavation, and ditch maintenance activities within or adjacent to tidal marshes that could support CCR will be limited to the time period from September 1 to January 31 to avoid the CCR breeding season.
- Travel on non-established roads/paths along the edges of tidal channels and sloughs will be minimized and the removal of native *Spartina* spp. will be minimized.

Action Area

The Action Area is defined as “all areas to be affected directly or indirectly by the Federal action and not merely the immediate area involved in the action,” (50 Code of Federal Regulations [CFR] 402.02). For the purpose of the effects assessment this includes all tidal marsh areas within the San Francisco Bay, the San Pablo Bay, and the Napa River estuary that are within the defined District boundaries. This includes approximately 11,600 acres for Marin and Sonoma Counties, approximately 2,400 acres for San Mateo County, approximately 1,071 acres for Alameda County, and approximately 6,300 acres for Napa County for a total of 21,371 acres. Please refer to the BA for maps of the specific County or District project sites.

ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK for the JEOPARDY DETERMINATION

Section 7(a)(2) of the Act requires that Federal agencies ensure that any action they authorize, fund, or carry out is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species. “Jeopardize the continued existence of” means to engage in an action that reasonably would be expected, directly or indirectly, to reduce appreciably the likelihood of both the survival and recovery of a listed species in the wild by reducing the reproduction, numbers, or distribution of that species (50 CFR § 402.02).

The jeopardy analysis in this biological opinion considers the effects of the proposed Federal action, and any cumulative effects, on the range wide survival and recovery of the listed species. It relies on four components: (1) the *Status of the Species*, which describes the current range

wide condition of the species, the factors responsible for that condition, and its survival and recovery needs; (2) the *Environmental Baseline*, which analyzes the current condition of the species in the Action Area without the consequences to the listed species caused by the proposed action, the factors responsible for that condition, and the relationship of the Action Area to the survival and recovery of the species; (3) the *Effects of the Action*, which includes all effects that are caused by the proposed Federal action; and (4) the *Cumulative Effects*, which evaluates the effects of future, non-Federal activities in the Action Area on the species. The *Effects of the Action* and *Cumulative Effects* are added to the *Environmental Baseline* and in light of the status of the species, the Service formulates its opinion as to whether the proposed action is likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species.

Status of the Species

CCR

Information about the CCR biology and ecology is available in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California*, available at: https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP/20130923_TMRP_Books_Signed_FINAL.pdf (Service 2013). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' range-wide status, please refer to the California clapper rail 5-year Review, available at https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/tess/species_nonpublish/3088.pdf (Service 2020). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review. Threats evaluated during that review and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species with loss of habitat being the most significant effect.

SMHM

There are two subspecies of the salt marsh harvest mouse: the northern subspecies (*R. r. halicoetes*) and the southern subspecies (*R. r. raviventris*) both of which are listed as endangered. Information about the salt marsh harvest mouse biology and ecology is available in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California*, available at: https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP/20130923_TMRP_Books_Signed_FINAL.pdf (Service 2013). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. Threats evaluated during the drafting of the recovery plan and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species since its publication, with loss of habitat being the most significant effect. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' range-wide status, please refer to the salt marsh harvest mouse 5-year review at https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/tess/species_nonpublish/3630.pdf (Service 2021). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review.

Environmental Baseline

Environmental baseline refers to the condition of the listed species or its designated critical habitat in the Action Area, without the consequences to the listed species or designated critical habitat caused by the proposed action. The environmental baseline includes the past and present impacts of all Federal, State, or private actions and other human activities in the Action Area, the anticipated impacts of all proposed Federal projects in the Action Area that have already undergone formal or early section 7 consultation, and the impact of State or private actions

which are contemporaneous with the consultation in process. The consequences to listed species or designated critical habitat from ongoing agency activities or existing agency facilities that are not within the agency's discretion to modify are part of the *Environmental Baseline*.

Mosquito abatement activities within the tidal marsh habitats in the Action Area have been ongoing in their current form since 1976. The Corps initiated consultation for the project in 2015 and the Service issued a biological opinion on August 29, 2016 (Service File No. 08FBDT00-2015-F-0032). No documented occurrences of injury or death of CCR have been reported to the Service to date as a result of these activities.

California Clapper Rail

The Action Area is located within the Recovery Plan's San Pablo Bay and Central/South San Francisco Bay Recovery Units which includes suitable or restorable tideland habitats in the San Pablo and San Francisco Bays. CCR have been documented to occur within the Action Area and have the potential to be within the multiple tidal marshes of the project area footprint (California Department of Fish and Wildlife (CDFW) 2022). There are considerably large expanses of high quality habitat that occur in the Action Area that likely continue to support the CCR. Available tidal marsh habitats in the San Pablo and San Francisco Bay are space-limited due to encroaching human development and future impacts of predicted sea level rise are expected to result in loss of low marsh foraging habitat in addition to the loss of high marsh refugia.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

The Action Area is located within the Recovery Plan's San Pablo Bay and Central/South San Francisco Bay Recovery Units which includes suitable or restorable tideland habitats in the San Pablo and San Francisco Bays. The northern subspecies (*R. r. halicoetes*) is known to occur around the marsh habitats in and around San Pablo Bay while the southern subspecies (*R. r. raviventris*) is known to occur in and around the marsh habitats in the San Francisco Bay. SMHM have been documented to occur within the Action Area and have the potential to be within the multiple tidal marshes of the project area footprint (CDFW 2022). There are considerably large expanses of high quality habitat that occur in the Action Area that likely continue to support the SMHM. The SMHM shares many of the same tidal marsh habitats as the CCR and is therefore under the same limited habitat availability and the threat of loss by predicted sea level rise.

Effects of the Proposed Action

Effects of the action are all consequences to listed species or critical habitat that are caused by the proposed action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed action. A consequence is caused by the proposed action if it would not occur but for the proposed action and it is reasonably certain to occur. Effects of the action may occur later in time and may include consequences occurring outside the immediate area involved in the action. The project will result in direct and indirect effects to listed species through disturbance of salt marsh habitat. Adverse effects and disturbance to habitat will be caused by foot traffic, vehicle traffic, mechanical ditching and the side casting of material.

The project may also result in beneficial effects through the maintenance of these marsh habitats. The various marsh ditches and canals that are targeted for maintenance are typically choked in with sedimentation and vegetation and have become hydrologically non-functioning resulting in a reduction of habitat quality. Marsh areas restricted from a hydrologic tidal exchange can create drier soils that can encourage invasive plant recruitment which in turn alters the marsh habitat. By re-opening the ditches and canals, the hydrologic function can return and supply an exchange of nutrients in and out of the marsh, maintain wet soil environments, and encourage native plant growth which improves habitat quality.

CCR

The proposed project will likely generate temporary noise and visual disturbance from personnel and equipment. Equipment noise, vibration, and visual disturbance may interfere with the normal behaviors of CCR if present in the project area or immediately nearby. These behaviors include feeding, sheltering, reproducing, rearing, movement between refugia and foraging grounds, and other essential behaviors. Affected CCR may suffer from increased predation, competition, and reduced reproductive success. Implementation of the project outside of the CCR breeding season will reduce the amount of disturbance to the species since the birds will not be holding territories or tending to nests or chicks and the potential for direct injury and mortality to CCR is anticipated to be very low or even zero based on the discrete localized effort within the various habitats, the proposed conservation measures, and the fact that no previous occurrences of injury or mortality have been reported to the Service as a result of these activities in the past.

The project will result in temporary adverse effects by removing vegetation and altering suitable habitat in the various ditches and canals. The total area of temporary impact can vary year to year as the project varies in total activity and scope. CCR may avoid these altered ditches and canals which will subsequently likely temporarily disrupt normal behavior patterns such as sheltering and feeding until such time as the habitat returns to suitability or the CCR doesn't perceive a threat. It is possible that ditch clearing efforts may be beneficial as it could provide shoreline conditions along the canal edges which would provide better habitat conditions for their prey base and thus provide better feeding opportunities for the CCR.

SMHM

The proposed project will likely generate temporary noise and visual disturbance from personnel and equipment. Equipment noise, vibration, and visual disturbance may interfere with the normal behaviors of SMHM if present in the project area or immediately nearby. These behaviors include feeding, sheltering, reproducing, rearing, movement between refugia and foraging grounds, and other essential behaviors. Affected SMHM may suffer from increased predation, competition, and reduced reproductive success. Project activities may cause actively nursing mice nearby to abandon their nests leading to mortality of their pups.

Intolerable levels of disturbance may force individual SMHM to flush from cover and expose themselves to contact with construction personnel and equipment. SMHM that come into contact with construction personnel or equipment are at risk of being trampled or crushed which could result in injury or mortality. If SMHM were utilizing access roads while moving through the Action Area, they could be killed by being crushed under passenger vehicles driving on the

access roads at the time of the incident. SMHM could also get injured or killed if they were to come in contact with vegetation clearing equipment.

The project will result in temporary adverse effects by removing vegetation and altering suitable habitat in the various ditches and canals. The total area of temporary impact can vary year to year as the project varies in total activity and scope. SMHM will likely avoid these altered ditches and canals which will subsequently likely disrupt normal behavior patterns such as sheltering and feeding until such time as the habitat returns to suitability.

These adverse effects are anticipated to be minimized through implementation of the proposed conservation measures which includes a project personnel training program and minimizing the total area disturbed by project activities.

Cumulative Effects

Cumulative effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local, or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the action area considered in this biological opinion. Future Federal actions that are unrelated to the proposed project are not considered in this section; they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act. During this consultation, the Service did not identify any future non-federal actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area of the proposed project.

Conclusion

After reviewing the current *Status of the Species*, the *Environmental Baseline*, the *Effects of the Action*, and the *Cumulative Effects*, it is the Service's biological opinion that the proposed Continued Maintenance of Existing Water Circulation Ditches for the Purpose of Mosquito Abatement in Tidal Marshes for Alameda, Napa, Marin, San Mateo, and Sonoma Counties, California Project is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the CCR or the SMHM. This is based on the current status and distribution of the CCR and SMHM populations range-wide, implementation of the *Conservation Measures* to minimize the adverse effects on individual CCR and SMHM and their habitats during project activities, and the small temporary impact to habitat in a localized area. There is also the potential for habitat improvements from improved aquatic flow in the tidal marshes from the clearing of the various ditches targeted for mosquito abatement.

INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9 of the Act and Federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened species, respectively, without special exemption. Take is defined as to harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harm in the definition of "take" in the Act means an act which actually kills or injures wildlife. Such [an] act may include significant habitat modification or degradation where it actually kills or injures wildlife by significantly impairing essential behavioral patterns, including breeding, feeding, or sheltering (50 CFR 17.3). Under the terms of section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking that is incidental to and not the purpose of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act provided that such taking is in

compliance with the proposed protective measures and the terms and conditions of an incidental take statement and occurs as a result of the action as proposed.

The measures described below are non-discretionary, and must be undertaken by the Corps so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the applicant, as appropriate, for the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. The Corps has a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If the Corps (1) fails to assume and implement the terms and conditions or (2) fails to require the applicant to adhere to the terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse. In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, the Corps must report the progress of the action and its impact on the species to the Service as specified in the incidental take statement [50 CFR §402.14(i)(3)].

Amount or Extent of Take

The Service anticipates incidental take of CCR will be difficult to detect or quantify because of their inherently elusive behavior, propensity to move rapidly through vegetation, and their cryptic occupancy in tidal marsh habitats resulting in low detectability. Therefore, the Service anticipates incidental take of all CCR within the approximate 21,371 acres of the Action Area in the form of harm from the impairment of essential behaviors through the noise, vibration, and visual effects of project activities. The Service anticipates that take of CCR will be low because project actions are described to be small discrete events within the entirety of the Action Area and the applicants' implementation of the proposed avoidance and minimization measures. Upon implementation of the following reasonable and prudent measure, take in the form of harm from impairing essential behaviors within the 21,371 acre Action Area will become exempt from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act. Injury or mortality to CCR is not anticipated to occur based on the Corps' proposal to incorporate the applicant's conservation measures; therefore, take in the form of injury or mortality will not be exempt from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act.

SMHM

The Service anticipates incidental take of SMHM will be difficult to detect or quantify because of their inherently elusive behavior, propensity to move rapidly through vegetation, and their cryptic occupancy in tidal marsh habitats resulting in low detectability. Therefore, the Service anticipates incidental take of all SMHM within the approximate 21,371 acres of the Action Area in the form of harm from the impairment of essential behaviors through the noise, vibration, and visual effects of project activities. Upon implementation of the following reasonable and prudent measure, take in the form of harm from impairing essential behaviors within the 21,371-acre Action Area will become exempt from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act.

The Service anticipates that take in the form of harm from wounding or killing of SMHM during implementation of project activities may occur due to the nature of the project, locations, and activity within high quality suitable habitat. It is difficult to determine the number of SMHM that could be injured or killed due to their small size and difficulty in finding individuals that may have succumb to their injuries and expired in the tidal marsh where they could not be detected. The number also does not include undetectable nursing pups or young mice that expire from

being abandoned in their nests. The number of undetected individuals that may be injured or killed from the project is anticipated to be small relative to the overall population of SMHM. The population will likely take a temporary small reduction in numbers at any of the given locations during the time of a project activity, but is expected to recover within the year. Upon implementation of the following reasonable and prudent measure, take in the form of harm from injury and mortality within the 21,371-acre Action Area will become exempt from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act.

Effect of the Take

In the accompanying biological opinion, the Service determined that this level of anticipated take is not likely to result in jeopardy to the CCR or the SMHM.

Reasonable and Prudent Measure

The Service has determined that the following Reasonable and Prudent Measure is necessary and appropriate to minimize the effects of the Continued Maintenance of Existing Water Circulation Ditches for the Purpose of Mosquito Abatement in Tidal Marshes for Alameda, Napa, Marin, San Mateo, and Sonoma Counties, California Project on the species:

1. Adverse effects to the CCR and SMHM shall be minimized to the fullest extent possible.

Term and Condition

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, the Corps shall comply with the following term and condition, which implement the Reasonable and Prudent measure described above. This Term and Condition is nondiscretionary. The following Term and Condition implement the Reasonable and Prudent Measure:

1. The project applicant shall fully implement the proposed project, including the conservation measures, the Reasonable and Prudent Measure, and the corresponding Term and Condition as described in this biological opinion.

Reporting Requirements

In order to monitor whether the amount or extent of incidental take anticipated from implementation of the project is approached or exceeded, the Corps shall adhere to the following reporting requirements. Should this anticipated amount or extent of incidental take be exceeded, the Corps must reinitiate formal consultation as per 50 CFR 402.16.

1. The Service must be notified within 24 hours of the finding of any injured or dead listed species or any unanticipated damage to its habitat associated with the proposed project. Injured listed species shall be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person. Notification will be made to the contact below in *Reporting Requirements*, and must include the date, time, and precise location of the individual/incident clearly indicated on a U.S. Geological Survey 7.5 minute quadrangle or other maps at a finer scale, as requested by the Service, and any other pertinent information. When an injured

or dead individual of the listed species is found, the Reclamation shall follow the steps outlined in the *Disposition of Individuals Taken* section below.

2. Sightings of any listed or sensitive animal species shall be reported to the Service and California Natural Diversity Database (<https://www.wildlife.ca.gov/Data/CNDDDB/Submitting-Data>).

Disposition of Individuals Taken

Injured listed species must be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person(s), such as a Service-approved biologist. Dead individuals must be sealed in a resealable plastic bag containing a paper with the date and time when the species was found, the location where it was found, the name of the person who found it, and the bag containing the specimen frozen in a freezer located in a secure site, until instructions are received from the Service regarding the disposition of the dead specimen. The Service contact person is Jana Affonso, Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at (916) 930-2664.

REINITIATION—CLOSING STATEMENT

This concludes formal consultation on the Continued Maintenance of Existing Water Circulation Ditches for the Purpose of Mosquito Abatement in Tidal Marshes for Alameda, Napa, Marin, San Mateo, and Sonoma Counties, California Project. As provided in 50 CFR §402.16,

- (a) Reinitiation of consultation is required and shall be requested by the Federal agency or by the Service, where discretionary Federal involvement or control over the action has been retained or is authorized by law and:
 - (1) If the amount or extent of taking specified in the incidental take statement is exceeded;
 - (2) If new information reveals effects of the action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not previously considered;
 - (3) If the identified action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in the biological opinion or written concurrence; or
 - (4) If a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the identified action.
- (b) An agency shall not be required to reinitiate consultation after the approval of a land management plan prepared pursuant to 43 U.S.C. 1712 or 16 U.S.C. 1604 upon listing of a new species or designation of new critical habitat if the land management plan has been adopted by the agency as of the date of listing or designation, provided that any authorized actions that may affect the newly listed species or designated critical habitat will be addressed through a separate action-specific consultation. This

exception to reinitiation of consultation shall not apply to those land management plans prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604 if:

- (1) Fifteen years have passed since the date the agency adopted the land management plan prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604; and
- (2) Five years have passed since the enactment of Public Law 115-141 [March 23, 2018] or the date of the listing of a species or the designation of critical habitat, whichever is later.

Please address any questions or concerns regarding this response to Brian Hansen, Senior Fish and Wildlife Biologist, at Brian_Hansen@fws.gov or (916) 930-5642 or Kim Squires, Section 7 Division Manager, at Kim_Squires@fws.gov. Please refer to Service file number 2022-0048737-S7-001 in any future correspondence regarding this project.

Sincerely,

Donald Ratcliff
Field Supervisor

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